

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR MANNITOL CONTENT IN ANTICOAGULANT SOLUTIONS OF BLOOD BAGS (SAGM) BY HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY USING REFRACTIVE INDEX DETECTOR

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ABSTRACT

A simple, reproducible method for quantification of Mannitol was developed and validated by using HPLC-Refractive Index detector. Chromatographic conditions for quantification of Mannitol were L19 column using water as mobile phase and Refractive index detector. The developed method is validated and established LOD & LOQ as 100ppm & 250ppm respectively. Recovery studies were performed and result is found to be in the range of 97-104%.

INTRODUCTION

Anticoagulants solution are used in blood bags to prevent it from clotting and achieve their effect by suppressing the synthesis or function of various clotting factors that are normally present in the blood. SAGM solution is used as an anticoagulant solution and its main constituents are saline, adenine, glucose, Mannitol. Chemically, Mannitol is a type of sugar alcohol used as sweetener and medication. Chemically, It is derived from sugar (Mannose)¹. Mannitol is C₆H₁₄O₆. Structure of Mannitol given in **figure.1** and it is in the osmotic diuretic family of medication. Function of Mannitol in

anticoagulant solution is free radical scavenger and membrane stabilizer preventing them from haemolysis. Hence, presence of Mannitol in anticoagulant solution increases the shelf life of red blood corpuscles.

Figure.1: Structure of mannitol

There are various methods reported in the literature for determination of Mannitol by enzymatic method (2-3), UPLC MS/MS method (4), gas-liquid method (5-7) and High performance liquid chromatographic method with light scattering detector (8) in urine. Literatures are available for estimation of Mannitol in biomedical samples like urine, digestive part using LC MS/MS technique (9-11). Gas chromatographic method is available for determination of Mannitol in olive tree roots (12). In published literature, liquid chromatographic reported method for Mannitol analysis are based on use of amino and HILIC columns. As per the available literature, there is no method published for quantification of Mannitol in anticoagulant solution using RID detector. In this present study, a simple, accurate method was developed and validated for estimation of Mannitol in anticoagulant solution used in blood bags for blood collection. The developed and validated method can be adopted for analysis in respective laboratories.

Experimental

Method Development:

Chemical and Reagents:

HPLC grade water, reference standard of mannitol having purity 99.3 %, Make: Asian research foundation.

Instrumentation and Analytical Conditions:

HPLC separation was achieved on Shimadzu liquid chromatographic system make, 2010HT model, equipped with RID detector, 100 μ L syringe capacity, HPLC column Oven (up to temperature 90 $^{\circ}$ C). The chromatographic separation was achieved on L19 Column (300mm X 7.8mm ID, CA+, Particle size 9 μ m) using water as mobile phase, injection volume 10 μ l, run time 20 minutes, column temperature 85 $^{\circ}$ C, RID temperature 40 $^{\circ}$ C with the flow rate of 1.0 ml/min.

Standard preparation:

Prepared 10000 μ g/ml Mannitol standard solution in HPLC grade water. Aliquots of the stock solution were appropriately

diluted with HPLC grade water to obtained 1000 μ g/ml standard solution of mannitol.

Sample preparation:

Sample solution eq. to 10 mg of mannitol was transferred into 10 ml volumetric flask and further diluted to volume using HPLC grade water to achieve 1000 μ g/concentration of Mannitol in sample solution.

Note: Used freshly prepared standard and sample solutions.

Method Validation:

This method was validated for specificity, linearity and precision (system precision and method precision) accuracy and robustness, limit of detection and limit of quantification. Method precision was performed with six samples preparation of nominal concentration (1000 μ g/ml) while accuracy was performed on limit of quantification to 150 %. Five points linearity was established by injecting standards 250, 500, 750, 1000, 1500 μ g/ml. The standard concentration and area was subjected to correlation coefficient calculation.

Specificity

To establish specificity, blank solution, standard solution and sample solution were injected in to HPLC system and response for Mannitol content was observed. There is no peak observed in blank chromatogram with the retention time of mannitol content. Retention time of Mannitol in the standard and test chromatogram was observed at 11.4 minutes. Chromatogram of blank, standard and test preparation is given in **Figure: 2, 3 and 4** respectively.

Figure 2: Blank Chromatogram **Figure 3: Standard chromatogram** **Figure 4: Sample chromatogram.**

Linearity

Linearity of an analytical method is its ability (within the range) to obtained test results that are directly proportional to the concentration of analyte. To establish the linearity, concentration range 250, 500, 750, 1000 and 1500µg/ml (ppm) was selected and 10µl of each linearity solution was injected in to HPLC system. Calibration curve was found to be linear in the range of 250-1500 µg/ml (ppm). Result of linearity plot of Mannitol are given in **Figure.5.**

Figure 5: Linearity plot Mannitol

Precision

Precision of the method was checked and verified by system precision and method precision. The system precision was measured on six injection of standard solution containing mannitol. The method precision of an analytical method is the amount of variation in the results obtained from multiple analysis of a homogenous sample (method precision). System precision was checked by injecting 10µl of standard preparation of mannitol

(concentration 1000µg/mL)in six replicates and % RSD was calculated by the area obtained from the injection of Mannitol. % RSD obtained 0.6%.

Method precision was calculated by injecting 6 sample preparations on Day-1(Inter-day) and different day(intra-day) using mentioned concentration of standard and sample solutions. Peak area measured was expressed in the terms of percent relative standard deviation (%RSD).The

Table 2. Shows combined result of method precision (inter-day & intra-day).

Table: 2. Results of Method precision

	% RSD standard (1000µg/mL)	% RSD sample preparation (1000µg/mL)
Day I	0.60	1.98
Day II	0.20	3.40
Day I & II (Avg.)	0.40	2.14

Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ):

Limit of detection and quantification was separately determined on the basis of signal to noise ratio and % RSD of injected standard solution was calculated. LOD is

established on S/N ratio. % RSD for LOD 11.36 % and 1.8 % for LOQ.

Figure 6: LOD standard chromatogram. **Figure 7:** LOQ standard chromatogram.

Accuracy (Recovery)

The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of test results obtained by that method to the true value or an accepted reference value. The accuracy of method was determined by calculating percentage recovery of known added amount of analyte. Recovery study was performed by spiking known concentration of standard solution in samples preparation at four different concentration levels i.e. LOQ level ,50% level, 100% level and 150%. Recovery falls in range of 80-120 % and results of recovery study given in the **Table 3**.

Table: 3 Results of recovery study.

Recovery At LOQ % Level (250ppm)					
	Original conc.	Observed conc.	Original conc. - Observed conc.	Spiked conc.	% recovery
Sample A	1046	1299	253	250	101
Sample B	1046	1305	259	250	104
Sample C	1046	1297	251	250	100
Recovery At 50 % Level (500ppm)					
Sample A	1046	1570	524	500	105
Sample B	1046	1555	509	500	102
Sample C	1046	1539	493	500	99
Recovery At 100 % Level(1000ppm)					
Sample A	1046	2013	967	1000	97
Sample B	1046	2020	974	1000	97
Sample C	1046	2039	993	1000	99
Recovery At 150 % Level (1500ppm)					
Sample A	1046	2505	1459	1500	97
Sample B	1046	2529	1483	1500	99
Sample C	1046	2528	1482	1500	99

Robustness

As per ICH guidelines robustness of an analytical procedure refers to its capability to remain unaffected by small and deliberate variation in the method (13). To determine the robustness of the developed method, minor changes were made in the flow rate of mobile phase. Standard and samples were injected and % RSD calculated. % RSD of samples result was within the range of 5%.

Conclusion:

The present study was carried out to develop a sensitive, precise and accurate HPLC-RID method for the analysis of Mannitol in anticoagulant solution (Blood bags-SAGM). Under the given chromatographic condition, developed method is found to be capable of quantitative determination of Mannitol in anticoagulant solution. The developed method was validated with respect to various parameters i.e. Specificity, linearity, accuracy, robustness, LOD & LOD. In specificity parameter, no peak

was observed for Mannitol in blank whereas, in standard and sample chromatogram a well resolved peak clearly shows that this method is specific for the quantitative analysis of Mannitol. In order to test linearity of this developed method, five levels of standard solutions were prepared in range of 250-1500 µg/ml and calibration curve was plot between areas versus concentrations. The correlation coefficient results was found to be 0.9989 which is within the acceptance criteria. Low variation was found in recoveries study in the spiked sample preparations, results were found to be in the range of 100-104 % (LOQ level), 99-105 % (50 % level), 97-99 % (100 % level) and 97-99 % (150 % level). Limit of detection achieved in the proposed method is 100ppm and limit of quantitation is 250ppm. In robustness study (change in flow rate), six samples preparation were analysed and result of standard deviation and relative standard deviation of results of Mannitol content are within the limits. Hence the developed HPLC-RID method can be adopted apparently for analysis of Mannitol in anticoagulant solution (Blood bags).

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